

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Diacetone Alcohol by Cerium(IV) in H₂SO₄ Medium

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Manuscript received 25 November 1988, accepted 25 April 1989

The kinetics of Ru^{III}-catalysis in Ce^{IV}-diacetone alcohol (DAA) redox system have been studied and the orders found to be unity in [Ce^{IV}] and fractional each in [DAA] and [Ru^{III}]. The rate increased with increase in [H⁺] at constant ionic strength but decreased at varying ionic strength. The increase in [HSO₄⁻] or [SO₄²⁻] decreased the rate. A mechanism involving a complex formation between DAA and Ru^{III} in a fast step which is oxidised by Ce^{IV} in a slow step to Ru^{IV}-complex is proposed and discussed.

THE use of transition metal ions like Os^{VIII}, Ru^{III}, Ru^{VIII} and Ir^{III}, either alone or as binary mixtures as homogeneous catalysts in the oxidation of several organic compounds by various oxidants is of recent interest¹. The mechanism of catalysis depends on the nature of the substrate, the oxidant and other experimental conditions. It has been shown that metal ions act as catalysts by one of the following paths: (i) the catalyst is first oxidised by the oxidant (OX) to its higher oxidation state which in subsequent fast step oxidises the substrate, (ii) the catalyst itself first oxidises the substrate in slow step, and the reduced form of the catalyst is then oxidised by the oxidant in a fast step resulting in a zero order dependence of rate on [oxidant] and first order dependence in [substrate] and [catalyst], (iii) the catalyst forms a complex with the substrate and the complex is then oxidised by the oxidant either in rate determining or in a fast step showing a rate dependence on [substrate], [catalyst] and [oxidant], and (iv) the catalyst traps the radicals produced as intermediates and oxidises the latter in a fast step.

In continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation of DAA by Ce^{IV} catalysed by different metal ions², we report here some of the kinetics results on the Ru^{III} catalysis in Ce^{IV}-DAA redox system.

Experimental

Ceric ammonium sulphate, ferrous ammonium sulphate, sulphuric acid were of AnalaR grade and used as such. RuCl₃ (Johnson-Mathew) solution was prepared and standardised^{3,4}. Diacetone alcohol (A.R.) was purified before use. All the experiments were conducted in aqueous H₂SO₄ medium under pseudo-first order conditions using ten-fold excess of substrate over the oxidant, and

the rate of reaction was measured by following the disappearance of Ce^{IV} volumetrically. CH₃COCH₃, CH₃COOH and HCOOH were identified as the products of oxidation by their characteristic tests⁵. Stoichiometric studies indicated that six moles of Ce^{IV} consumed for each mole of DAA,

Results and Discussion

The results pertain to the conditions where the uncatalysed reaction is negligible and the catalyst is always added to the solution before the addition of Ce^{IV}. The kinetic results are summarised as follows. (i) Under the conditions [Ce^{IV}] ≪ [DAA] the order in [Ce^{IV}] is unity as can be seen from the linear plot of log a/(a-x) vs time which passes through the origin (Fig. 1A). (ii) The order in [DAA] changed from unity in the absence of catalyst to fraction (0.68) in the presence of catalyst as is seen from the slope of linear plot of log k' vs log [DAA] (Fig. 1B), where k' is the observed rate constant. (iii) The rate increased considerably with increase in Ru^{III} and the order in [Ru^{III}] was found to be fractional (0.70) (Fig. 1D). (iv) The rate also increased with increase in [H⁺] at constant ionic strength but decreased with increase in [H⁺] at varying ionic strength (Table 1). (v) The increase in [HSO₄⁻] or [SO₄²⁻] decreased the rate at constant [H⁺] (Table 2). (vi) A linear plot was obtained by plotting 1/k vs 1/[DAA] with an intercept on 1/k' axis (Fig. 1C). (vii) Polymerisation was observed when acrylonitrile was added to the reaction system indicating the presence of free radicals.

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of $\log a(a-x)$ vs time, $[Ce^{IV}] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[DAA] = 0.050 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ru^{III}] = 1.14 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (B) Plot of $3 + \log k'$ vs $2 + \log [DAA]$; $[DAA] = 2.50 - 10.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and other conditions same as in (A). (C) Plot of $10^{-3}/k''$ vs $10^{-2}/[DAA]$. (D) Plot of $2 + \log k_{obs}$ vs $6 + \log [Ru^{III}]$; $[Ru^{III}] = 1.14 - 3.73 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$ ON k' IN Ce^{IV} -DAA REACTION
 $[Ce^{IV}] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[DAA] = 0.050 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 318 K

$[H_2SO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	k' $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	k'' $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$
0.600	1.22	5.45
1.00	1.53	4.20
1.50	2.01	3.35
1.70	2.32	3.01
2.00	2.69	2.50

*The observed rate constant at varying ionic strength.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[HSO_4^-]$ AND $[SO_4^{2-}]$ ON RATE CONSTANT IN Ce^{IV} -DAA REACTION

$[Ce^{IV}] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[DAA] = 0.050 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 318 K

$[HSO_4^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$[SO_4^{2-}]$ mol dm^{-3}	k' $\times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$
0.00	0.00	4.22
0.400	0.00	4.01
0.600	0.00	3.45
1.00	0.00	2.96
1.52	0.00	2.80
0.00	0.60	1.54
0.00	1.00	1.15
0.00	1.60	0.959

The change of order in $[DAA]$ from unity in the absence of catalyst to fraction (0.68) in the presence of catalyst indicates that probably it is involved in complex formation either with Ce^{IV} or Ru^{III} . It was

reported earlier that alcohols do not form complexes with Ce^{IV} in H_2SO_4 medium⁶. The other possibility is complexation of DAA with Ru^{III} . Ru^{III} is known to form complexes with organic compounds containing oxygen atom⁷. Therefore, it is not unreasonable to assume a complex between DAA and Ru^{III} . The kinetic evidence for such complex formation comes from the fractional order dependence of rate on Ru^{III} and also forms Michaelis-Menten type of plot where a straight line is obtained by plotting $1/k'$ vs $1/[DAA]$ or $1/[Ru^{III}]$ with definite intercept on $1/k'$ axis (Fig. 1C). The spectral evidence for such a complex comes from the fact that λ_{max} of $RuCl_3$ solution (290 nm) shifted to longer wavelength (320 nm) in presence of DAA.

The state of Ce^{IV} in H_2SO_4 medium is complicated by the fact that sulphate being a better ligand can combine with Ce^{IV} to a varying degree forming various species. Several investigations^{8,9} revealed that in H_2SO_4 medium ceric sulphate exists mainly as $Ce(SO_4)_2^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_3$ and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ depending on the concentration of sulphate. From the study of the effect of $[H^+]$, $[HSO_4^-]$ or $[SO_4^{2-}]$ on rate it was concluded that neutral $Ce(SO_4)_3$ is the reactive species in the present investigation. The retardation of rate by the addition of sulphate or bisulphate may be attributed to the removal of reactive species, as in the following equilibria,

The accelerating effect of $[H^+]$ at constant ionic strength may be explained due to the presence of hydrolysis equilibria,

The reaction between Ce^{IV} -DAA involves the formation of radicals which were confirmed by polymerisation tests. The formation of $CH_3CO\dot{C}H_2$ radical as reactive intermediate as identified by the end-group analysis of the polymer formed. Radicals were also detected in presence of Ru^{III} .

From the ion-exchange studies¹⁰ it was confirmed that ruthenium trichloride forms $RuCl_3^{2-}$ species in HCl and aqution of this species to $[RuCl_3(H_2O)]^{2-}$ takes only a few seconds¹¹. Thus $[RuCl_3(H_2O)]^{2-}$ was assumed to be the reactive species in the present investigation.

Based on the above experimental observations, the probable mechanisms may be written as

Taking oxidation of Ru^{III}-DAA complex by Ce^{IV} as slow step, the rate law is derived as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{Kk''[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{DAA}][\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{1 + K[\text{DAA}] + K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (6)$$

or

$$\frac{-2.303 d \log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{Kk''[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{DAA}]}{1 + K[\text{DAA}] + K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (7)$$

which explains all the experimentally obtained results.

Taking reciprocal of equation (7),

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{[\text{DAA}]} \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{k''K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} + \frac{1}{k''} \right] + \frac{1}{k''[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \right\} \quad (8)$$

From equation (8) it is clear that plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{DAA}]$ should be linear with an intercept on $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ axis. Such plots have been observed in the present work confirming the general validity of the rate law and hence the mechanism. Ru^{IV} was also proposed as the reactive species in the Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of Hg⁺, *p*-benzoquinone and *p*-anisidine by Mn^{III}^{2,18}. From the slope and intercept

values of double-reciprocal plots, the bimolecular rate constant (k'') for the slow step and the formation constant (K) for the complex were evaluated. The activation parameters were determined and found to be $K = 11.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $E_{\text{exp}} = 42.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 39.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 49.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -32.6 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

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